

Acoustic studies of systems of aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons with 1-butanol at 298, 308 and 318 K and application of theoretical approaches

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The solvation behaviour of benzene and hexane with 1-butanol have been studied from sound speed (u), density (ρ) and viscosity (η) at three temperatures 298, 308 and 318 K. These data are used to calculate isentropic compressibility (K_s), intermolecular free length (L_f) and acoustic impedance (Z). The excess parameters for the systems viz. deviation in viscosity ($\Delta\eta$), deviation in isentropic compressibility (ΔK_s), excess intermolecular free length (L_f^E), excess acoustic impedance (Z^E), which are used in interpreting the extent and type of interactions in both the systems. The excess properties were fitted to the Redlich-Kister equation for the computation of smoothening coefficients. Weak interactions of dipole-induced dipole type are possible in the system. The validity of various theoretical approaches of liquids has been tested for the system under investigation, by comparing theoretical sound speeds with those experimentally determined over the entire composition range and at the temperatures taken for study. Free Length Theory is the best suited for such systems.

The acoustic, volumetric and viscometric behaviour has been proved to be very useful in elucidating the various interactions occurring in liquid mixtures. Extensive information on acoustic properties of binary mixtures of benzene and hexane with 1-butanol are of significance because they are being increasingly used in many industrial processes.

In this paper we have reported some acoustic studies on the hexane-butanol and benzene-butanol mixtures to elucidate various interactions occurring in such systems.

Results and discussion

The experimentally measured density (ρ), sound speed (u) and viscosity (η) have been used to evaluate derived properties like intermolecular free length (L_f), isentropic compressibility (K_s), molar volume (V), acoustic impedance (Z) and excess parameters by using well-established relations¹,

$$L_f = \frac{K}{u\rho^{1/2}} \quad (1)$$

$$K_s = \frac{1}{u^2\rho} \quad (2)$$

$$V_{\text{mix}} = \frac{x_1M_1 + x_2M_2}{\rho_{\text{mix}}} \quad (3)$$

$$Z = u\rho \quad (4)$$

Excess parameters have been calculated from following equation,

$$Y^E = Y_{\text{mix}} - (x_1Y_1 + x_2Y_2) \quad (5)$$

where Y^E is ΔK_s , L_f^E , V^E , $\Delta\eta$ and Z^E .

All the excess parameters are fitted to Redlich-Kister polynomial equation to estimate the adjustable parameters,

$$Y^E = x_1x_2 \sum_{i=0}^2 A_i (1-2x)^i \quad (6)$$

where x_1 stands for the mole fractions of benzene and hexane respectively and x_2 stands for mole fraction 1-butanol, A_i is the smoothening coefficient and Y^E represent the theoretical excess functions. The standard deviation was evaluated by using the following relation :

$$\sigma(Y^E) = \left[\frac{(Y_{\text{obs}}^E - Y_{\text{cal}}^E)^2}{n-p} \right]^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

where n is the total number of experimental points and p is the number of A_i coefficients considered ($p = 3$ in present case).

The theoretical values of sound speeds are evaluated using the following relationships :

Sound speed by Jacobson's Free Length Theory is calculated using the following formula²,

$$u^{FLT} = \frac{K}{L_{f \text{ mix}} \rho_{Exp}^{1/2}} \quad (8)$$

where K is Jacobson's constant depends only on temperature and $L_{f \text{ mix}}$ is intermolecular free length of mixture.

The empirical formula for sound speed in binary liquid mixtures given by Nomoto³ can be written as :

$$u^{NOM} = \left[\frac{x_1 R_1 + x_2 R_2}{x_1 V_1 + x_2 V_2} \right]^3 \quad (9)$$

where x , R and V represents mole fraction, molar sound speed and molar volume. Suffix 1 represents benzene and hexane respectively and suffix 2 represents 1-butanol respectively.

Vandael Vangaël ideal mixing relation is computed from the following formulas⁴

$$\frac{1}{x_1 M_1 + x_2 M_2} \frac{1}{u_{mix}^2} = \frac{x_1}{M_1 u_1^2} + \frac{x_2}{M_2 u_2^2} \quad (10)$$

where x_1 stands for the mole fractions of benzene and hexane respectively and x_2 stands for mole fraction 1-butanol and u_1 is sound speed for benzene and hexane respectively and u_2 is sound speed of 1-butanol.

The sound speed in the mixture is given by Impedance Dependence Relation as⁵,

$$u = \frac{\sum x_i Z_i}{x_i \rho_i} \quad (11)$$

Figs. 1 and 2 depicts the variation of ΔK_s and L_f for benzene + 1-butanol system and V^E , $\Delta \eta$ and Z^E for hexane + 1-butanol system taken as representative. Similar plots were recorded for all five excess functions for both the binaries. Fig. 3 shows the deviation of theoretical values of sound speeds at 298 K for benzene + 1-butanol and hexane + 1-butanol systems respectively. Density and acoustic impedance increases while η decreases for benzene + 1-butanol system. Sound speed decreases up to $x \sim 0.32$ mole fraction of benzene, thereafter showing a continuous increase for the system. K_s and L_f increases up to $x \sim 0.32$ mole fraction of benzene and thereafter decrease over the entire composition range. In hexane + 1-butanol system K_s and L_f shows a increase while u , ρ , η and Z shows a continuous decrease. Sound speed varies non-linearly in benzene + 1-butanol system. The non-linear variation of sound speed in the solution exhibits interactions in the system. It decreases with increase in L_f as a result of mixing of components⁶. V^E , ΔK_s and L_f^E are

Fig. 1. Hexane in hexane-butanol system. Variation of (a) molar volume (V^E) vs mole fraction, (b) viscosity ($\Delta \eta$) vs mole fraction and (c) acoustic impedance (Z^E) vs mole fraction; temp. (◆) 298, (■) 308, (▲) 318 K.

Fig. 2. Benzene in benzene-butanol system. Variation of (a) isentropic compressibility (ΔK_s) vs mole fraction, (b) intermolecular free length (L_f^E) vs mole fraction; temp. (◆) 298, (■) 308, (▲) 318 K.

positive for both the systems at the three temperatures while $\Delta \eta$ and Z^E are negative. Positive and negative deviation in these functions from rectilinear dependence on composition for the present systems is indicative of inter-

Fig. 3. Deviation of theoretically predicted sound speed values (u^{FLT} , u^{IDR} , u^{NOM} , u^{VAN}) from experimental values (in ms^{-1}) for the system (a) benzene-butanol and (b) hexane-butanol at 298 K. (\blacklozenge) u^{FLT} , (\blacksquare) u^{IDR} , (\blacktriangle) u^{NOM} , (\times) u^{VAN} .

actions between unlike molecules. The observed values of V^E , ΔK_s and L_f^E can be qualitatively explained by considering the factors influencing these functions, namely, (i) the mutual disruption of associates present in the pure liquids, (ii) the formation of weak bonds by dipole-induced dipole interaction between unlike molecules, (iii) geometrical fitting of component molecules into each others structure. The first factor contributes to positive V^E , ΔK_s and L_f^E , while the remaining two factors lead to negative V^E , ΔK_s and L_f^E values. The observed positive values of V^E , ΔK_s and L_f^E for both the binaries over whole composition range suggest that the dispersion forces are dominant over the weak dipole-induced dipole bonding between unlike molecules, making V^E , ΔK_s and L_f^E values positive. It is interesting to note that V^E , ΔK_s and L_f^E values are more positive in 1-butanol rich region which shows pronounced mutual dissociation of 1-butanol associates. Further, possibility of interstitial accommodation is ruled out due to very less difference between the molar volumes of components in both the binaries. Similar results have also been reported by others for toluene + 1-butanol, $\text{CHF}_3\text{CH}_2\text{OH} + \text{C}_6\text{H}_6$, methyl cyclohexyl amine + benzene, 1-propanol + decane, alkyl acetate + n-hexane, heptane + 1-butanol⁷.

The peak obtained for V^E , ΔK_s and L_f^E in both the systems can be attributed to the depolymerisation of 1-butanol due to addition of increasing amounts of benzene and hexane respectively in the two systems. This increases the excess molar volume and excess intermolecular free

length making the system highly compressible and hence an increase in V^E , ΔK_s and L_f^E is observed till a maxima is obtained. Due to this breaking of self associations in 1-butanol molecules small entities are formed which creates induced dipoles in their vicinity leading to very weak interactions of dipole-induced dipole type in the system. This behaviour continues and the mixtures become richer in benzene and hexane. Due to these interactions V^E , ΔK_s and L_f^E decreases and also the mixture is now not only easily compressible causing decrease in K_s . This explains the observed peak in the excess V^E , ΔK_s and L_f^E versus composition profiles in the two systems.

$\Delta\eta$ and Z^E are negative over the entire range of composition. The negative deviation in $\Delta\eta$ and Z^E values are supported by the positive deviation of V^E , ΔK_s and L_f^E for the systems. A maxima is observed at $x \sim 0.32$ mole fraction in benzene + 1-butanol system and $x \sim 0.36$ in hexane + 1-butanol system due to depolymerisation of self association by breakup of hydrogen bonding of 1-butanol with the addition of dissimilar non-polar molecule leading to formation of small dipoles in the system. The decrease in $\Delta\eta$ after attaining a maxima indicates a possibility of weak interactions of dipole-induced dipole type with increasing number of small dipoles in the mixture. As the concentration of 1-butanol decreases in both the systems, the negative deviation of $\Delta\eta$ and Z^E decreases and the system tends towards ideality. Similar deviation are observed for acetone + cyclohexane and acetone + benzene system⁸. Fig. 3, taken as representative figures shows the percentage deviation in sound speed values calculated by various theoretical approaches for benzene + 1-butanol and hexane + 1-butanol system at 298 K respectively. Figures at 308 and 318 K have also been plotted. Free Length Theory is found to be best applicable theory for theoretical sound speed while Impedance Dependence Relation is having maximum deviation for benzene + 1-butanol system and Nomoto Relation for hexane + 1-butanol system. The order of applicability of various theoretical sound speed values for benzene + 1-butanol and hexane + 1-butanol system is $u^{FLT} > u^{VAN} > u^{NOM} > u^{IDR}$ and $u^{FLT} > u^{IDR} > u^{VAN} > u^{NOM}$ respectively.

From the above discussion it is concluded that interactions are possible in the binary systems of benzene + 1-butanol and hexane + 1-butanol and the system tends to show ideal behaviour as the temperature is increased.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. Benzene (Merck), hexane (s d fine) and 1-butanol (Merck)

with purity >99% were used after drying by standard procedures⁹. The densities of pure liquids and mixtures were measured using a precalibrated bicapillary pycnometer, the accuracy of data being within $\pm 0.057\%$, sound speed was measured by single crystal ultrasonic interferometer at 2 MHz frequency and data were accurate upto $\pm 0.03\%$. Viscosity was measured using Ostwald's viscometer and the accuracy fell within $\pm 0.09\%$. All measurements were made in a thermostatically controlled water bath with temperature accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$. The purity of the components was ascertained by comparing the boiling point, density and viscosity of pure components with those reported in literature⁹.

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